

Correction

Correction: Zammit et al. Association between the Concentration and the Elemental Composition of Outdoor PM_{2.5} and Respiratory Diseases in Schoolchildren: A Multicenter Study in the Mediterranean Area. *Atmosphere* 2020, 11, 1290

Christopher Zammit ¹, David Bilocca ^{1,*}, Silvia Ruggieri ² and on behalf of the RESPIRA Collaborative Project Group [†]

- ¹ Department of Medicine, University of Malta, 2080 Msida, MSD, Malta; christopher.a.zammit@gov.mt (C.Z.); martin.balzan@gov.mt (M.B.); stephen.montefort@um.edu.mt (S.M.)
- ² National Research Council of Italy, Institute Biomedical Research and Innovation, 90146 Palermo, Italy; silvia.ruggieri@irib.cnr.it (S.R.); gaspare.drago@irib.cnr.it (G.D.); giovanni.viegi@ibim.cnr.it (G.V.); fabio.cibella@ibim.cnr.it (F.C.)
- ³ National Research Council of Italy, Institute of Atmospheric Pollution Research, 00015 Monterotondo, Italy; perrino@iia.cnr.it
- ⁴ Department of Chemistry, Sapienza University of Rome, 00185 Rome, Italy; silvia.canepari@uniroma1.it
- * Correspondence: david.bilocca@gov.mt
- [†] The Indoor and Outdoor Air Quality and Respiratory Health in Malta and Sicily—RESPIRA Collaborative Study Group: Martin Balzan, Charles Borg, Stephen Montefort, Salvatore Bucchieri, Fabio Cibella, Paolo Colombo, Giuseppina Cuttitta, Gaspare Drago, Giuliana Ferrante, Luca L'Abbate, Stefania La Grutta, Valeria Longo, Mario R Melis, Silvia Ruggieri, Giovanni Viegi, Remo Minardi, Giuseppe Piva, Rosaria Ristagno, Gianfranco Rizzo, Gianluca Scaccianoe.

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In the original article [1], there was a mistake in the legend for Figure 6. The correct legend appears below. The authors apologize for any inconvenience caused and state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. The original article has been updated.

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the relationships between prevalence (and 95% confidence interval) of doctor diagnosis of asthma, current asthma, use of medicine for asthma in the last 12 months, and rhinitis in the last 12 months, and outdoor vanadium concentration (mean and 95% confidence interval) per each community (Cos/Zej: Cospicua/Zejtun).

In the original article, there were some mistakes in Table 1 as published. Due to a material error, most of the percentages (not the absolute values) in the table were erroneously indicated. The corrected Table 1 appears below. The authors apologize for any inconvenience caused and state that the scientific conclusions are unaffected. The original article has been updated.

Table 1. Characteristics of the study sample (total no. = 2050). The characteristics of each community (urban, rural, industrial) are also indicated.

	Malta (No. = 860)			Italy (No. = 1190)			
	Hamrun Urban/Industrial (No. = 341)	Cospicua/Zejtun Industrial (No. = 235)	Mosta Rural (No. = 284)	Gela Industrial (No. = 593)	Niscemi Rural (No. = 314)	Butera Rural (No. = 119)	Mazzarino Rural (No. = 164)
General characteristics							
Age Years, mean (\pm SD)	12.9 (\pm 0.7)	12.5 (\pm 0.7)	12.1 (\pm 0.5)	11.8 (\pm 1.1)	11.7 (\pm 1.1)	11.9 (\pm 1.1)	12.0 (\pm 1.1)
Male/Female (No.)	157/184	101/134	120/164	296/297	154/160	61/58	83/81
Parental atopy No. (%)	41 (12.0%)	30 (12.8%)	29 (10.2%)	59 (10.0%)	32 (10.2%)	9 (7.6%)	8 (4.9%)
Crowding index > 1 No. (%)	147 (43.1%)	88 (37.4%)	108 (38.0%)	179 (30.2%)	78 (24.8%)	37 (31.1%)	55 (33.5%)
Respiratory health							
Acute respiratory disease in the first 2 yrs No. (%)	43 (12.6%)	33 (14.0%)	40 (14.1%)	168 (28.3%)	102 (32.5%)	24 (20.2%)	59 (36.0%)
Doctor diagnosed asthma No. (%)	63 (18.5%)	48 (20.4%)	44 (15.5%)	57 (9.6%)	22 (7.0%)	3 (2.5%)	7 (4.3%)
Current asthma No. (%)	28 (8.2%)	18 (7.7%)	21 (7.4%)	22 (3.7%)	8 (2.5%)	2 (1.7%)	3 (1.8%)
Asthma medication 12 months No. (%)	40 (11.7%)	36 (15.3%)	28 (9.9%)	40 (6.7%)	15 (4.8%)	1 (0.8%)	2 (1.2%)
Rhinitis 12 months No. (%)	106 (31.1%)	61 (26.0%)	68 (23.9%)	171 (28.8%)	61 (19.4%)	18 (15.1%)	30 (18.3%)
Home Exposures							
Dampness exposure No. (%)	81 (23.8%)	20 (8.5%)	47 (16.5%)	73 (12.3%)	34 (10.8%)	14 (11.7%)	20 (12.2%)
Domestic exposure to tobacco smoke No. (%)	77 (22.6%)	37 (15.7%)	52 (18.3%)	101 (17.0%)	88 (28.0%)	25 (21.0%)	27 (16.5%)
Pets No. (%)	204 (59.8%)	145 (61.7%)	157 (55.3%)	145 (24.5%)	47 (15.0%)	14 (11.8%)	37 (22.6%)
Traffic No. (%)	97 (28.4%)	44 (18.7%)	59 (20.8%)	178 (30.0%)	56 (17.8%)	13 (10.9%)	33 (20.1%)

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Reference

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